

NECESSITY OF SEASONAL INFLUENZA VACCINATION PROPHYLAXIS

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Annual influenza epidemics have become one of the primary issues faced by modern healthcare due to the high morbidity and mortality, especially among the at risk groups from the population, and also because of the large spending for outpatient and in-patient care and the considerable strain on the entire health system. This article motivates the need for vaccine prophylaxis for seasonal influenza bearing with the purpose of reducing morbidity, complications and mortality related to this disease. In it, the basic presentation of influenza and its complications have been presented, along with the benefits of vaccinating against it to the individual, society and the health system. We have analysed the morbidity

Keywords: influenza, vaccine, prophylaxis

According to data from the influenza tracking system in Bulgaria annual influenza epidemics are a serious health problem faced by our country. On average, about 1 400 000 to 1 600 000 cases of acute respiratory infection (ARI) and influenza occur each year in regional cities alone.

According to the World Health Organization, seasonal influenza can affect up to 20% of the population, depending on which influenza viruses are circulating and can also cause high mortality. According to the latest figures, up to 650,000 people die each year from respiratory illnesses related to seasonal influenza, with up to 72,000 of these being in the WHO European Region.

The goal of this article is to substantiate the need for seasonal influenza vaccine prophylaxis with a view to reducing morbidity, complications and mortality related to this disease.

In order to achieve the goal of the study, the following tasks were set:

1. A description of the main presentations of influenza and its complications.
2. An analysis of the benefits of vaccination.
3. An analysis of influenza morbidity in the period 2019-2023.

Materials and research methodology.

To collect the necessary information, a documentary method was used with the study and analysis of data from regulatory documents and reports from the WHO, the National Statistical Institute, the National Center for Disease Control and Prevention, the Ministry of Health and the EU.

Influenza is an acute infectious disease, among the most contagious infections. It is caused by Influenza virus type A and Influenza virus type B. It is characterized by sharply pronounced infectiousness - high fever, headache, severe muscle pain and catarrhal inflammation of the upper respiratory tract. It is spread cyclically in the form of epidemics, which may occasionally can

develop into pandemics. It's highly contagious due to its short incubation period, airborne transmission mechanism and high susceptibility among humans. It can therefore spread quite intensively and cause seasonal epidemics annually. The disease is also characterised by the continuous variability in the antigenic structure of the influenza virus, which leads to universal susceptibility due to a lack of immunity to the strain circulating at a given time. Statistics show that the number of influenza illnesses exceeds the number of all other infections combined by several times. During pandemics, 30 to 50% of the world's population may be affected.

Influenza has both health and medico-social significance. This is due to its extensive spread, its severe course in children and the elderly, its high mortality rate, its paralysing effect on the entire activity of society and the enormous economic damage it causes.

The complications of influenza are characterised by various organ pathologies. Most often the damage is to the respiratory system - viral or bacterial laryngitis, tracheitis, bronchitis, pneumonia, empyema and abscess in the lung. Influenza otitis and purulent meningitis are possible.

Cardiovascular disorders come second - cardiovascular weakness, myocardial dystrophy, pericarditis. Phlebitis and thromboses of veins and arteries occur not infrequently.

Complications can also occur in the digestive system, presenting with loss of appetite, coated tongue, vomiting, feeling of and pain in the abdomen.

If the central nervous system is damaged the complications are - meningitis, encephalitis, myelitis, peripheral neuritis, parainfectious psychoses.

The main means of preventing influenza and reducing morbidity, mortality and severe complications is vaccination prophylaxis. Many cases of influenza, the associated severe complications and death can be prevented by raising the usage of modern seasonal influenza vaccines

Influenza immunisation is administered annually before or during the influenza season. Immunity develops only 1-2 weeks after vaccination and lasts for not less than 6 months. Due to the easy spread of influenza viruses, people of all age groups are at risk of infection. Because of the possible complications of the disease, however, young children and the those over the age of 65, as well as patients with comorbidities, are most vulnerable [1, 3].

Influenza vaccines are available globally and have been administered for more than 60 years. Modern influenza vaccines are characterised by excellent vaccine tolerability and effectiveness. In the elderly, the benefit of seasonal influenza immunization in reducing morbidity and mortality has been demonstrated compared to the same risk group with no vaccine administered.

Immunisation is particularly important for people at higher risk of serious complications from the illness and for the people who live with and take care of them. Seasonal influenza immunisation is also recommended to be carried on a yearly basis, before the start of and during the epidemic season. The continuous variability of influenza viruses leads to the need to update the composition of influenza vaccines annually, which is done on the recommendation of the WHO.

Influenza vaccination benefits the vaccinated person as well as society and the health care system, leading to epidemic containment [1,5].

The benefits to the vaccinated are as follows:

- Vaccination protects the vaccinated against severe illness and death.
- Vaccination reduces the vaccinated person's risk of subsequent complications and lasting health effects related to the disease.
- Vaccinated people are less likely to spread the infection to others - they are less likely to infect their

relatives, including the elderly, those with chronic conditions, those who are pregnant and children at risk of severe illness.

- Benefits to society:
 - Mass vaccination produces collective immunity and reduces the spread of the virus in the population. This reduces morbidity and mortality rates.
 - Higher vaccination coverage (achieving collective immunity) protects the most vulnerable groups, including people who cannot be vaccinated for medical reasons.
 - Vaccinated individuals are less likely to spread infection to others. In this sense, vaccination is also taking responsibility towards other members of society.
- Benefits for the health system:
 - Vaccinated people are less likely to get influenza and less likely to need to see their GP, be hospitalised, or need medical treatment. This significantly reduces pressure on the health system - hospital beds are freed up for non-influenza patients, more people have better and timely access to medicines used for the treatment of influenza and other illnesses.

The analysis of influenza and ARI incidence in the 2019-2023 period is presented based on data from the Influenza and Acute Respiratory Infections Information System and the results of laboratory surveillance of influenza virus circulation in that period.

In 2023, the observed sample included a total of 221 outpatient facilities serving 371 626 people, distributed in the following age groups: 0-4, 5-14, 15-29, 30-64 and 65+. The average annual number of population seen and the incidence by age group are presented in Table 1. [2]

Table 1

Influenza and Accute Respiratory Infection morbidity by age group for 2023

Age groups (years)	Annual average number of the population observed	Number registered cases	Morbidity per 10 000
0-4	17 721	26 377	14 884.60
5-14	37 095	37 665	10 153.66
15-29	58 337	26 338	4 514.80
30-64	188 057	34 462	1 832.53
65+	70 416	9 493	1 348.13
Total	371 626	134 335	3 614.79

Source: The Influenza and Acute Respiratory Infections Information System.

In 2023, a total of 134 335 influenza and ARI illnesses and an incidence rate of 3 614.79 per 10 000 population were registered. In comparison, in 2022, a total of 124 623 influenza and ARI illnesses and an incidence rate of 3 291.20 per 10 000 population were

registered (Table 2). During the examined period (2019-2023), a decrease in incidence was observed in 2020 and 2021, with a rise again in the following two years - 2022 and 2023.

Table 2

Influenza and Accute Respiratory Infection morbidity for the 2019-2023 period.

Years	Annual average number of the population observed	number registered cases	Morbidity per 10 000
2019	381 256	128 951	3 382.27
2020	380 211	104 612	2 751.42
2021	379 105	97 655	2 575.94
2022	378 655	124 623	3 291.20
2023	371 626	134 335	3 614.79

In Bulgaria, seasonal influenza usually appears in epidemic form in January and early February. The typical presentation of the epidemic wave can be observed for the 2023 period There is an increase in the intensity

of the epidemic process in the country, as well as an upsurge from the first week of the year. The morbidity starts to rise sharply and reaches a peak in week 3, after which it starts to decline gradually (Table 3).

Table 3

Influenza and Accute Respiratory Infection morbidity by age group for the 2023 epidemic period.

week No.	Period	Morbidity per 10 000 by age group (years)					Total morbidity
		0-4	5-14	15-29	30-64	65+	
1	01.01-08.01	441.61	328.14	161.30	69.92	60.67	126.16
2	09.01-15.01	689.31	495.69	232.90	103.87	80.89	187.04
3	16.01-22.01	724.61	561.80	242.29	106.25	80.18	197.90
4	23.01-29.01	604.12	440.82	204.19	86.21	77.76	163.42
5	30.01-05.02	572.18	342.06	161.98	70.61	50.84	132.40

Source: The Influenza and Acute Respiratory Infections Information System.

As in previous years, in 2023 the influenza and ARI morbidity is the highest in young children aged 0-4 years, followed by the 5-14 year age group.

Conclusion

According to global statistics, around 70 000 deaths from influenza are recorded annually in European Union (EU) member states, with up to 90% of these occurring in people over 65 years of age, mostly with co-morbidities. Globally, seasonal influenza epidemics cause 3 to 5 million cases of severe illness and 290 000 to 650 000 deaths every year. The large number of people affected at the same time sharply increases the need for outpatient and inpatient treatment and leads to an overstretched treatment network. Mortality from influenza-related diseases has been increasing over the years. The likely causes are the increased proportion of an ageing population, the intensive spread of new influenza strains, and improvements in influenza diagnostics, which make it possible to establish a causal link between influenza illness and subsequent complications and death.

All of these, together with the benefits of vaccination, justify the need for motivated vaccination for this infectious disease.

References:

- <https://plusmen.bg/>
- Vladimirova N., A. Minkova, N. Bogdanov, K. Petkova, Zh. Getsova, G. Kamenov, Acute Infectious Diseases in Bulgaria in 2023, p. 53 /in Bulgarian/, https://www.ncipd.org/images/UserFiles/File/Analizi/Analysis_ZB%20_2023%20FINAL.pdf /last visited 18 Nov 2024/
- Penchev D., D. Petkova, R. Zlatanova-Velikova, Public Attitudes, Awareness And Fears Related To The Spread Of Covid-19 In Bulgaria, Acta Medica Bulgarica, 05/2023; ISSN: 0324-1750, 50(2):60-65. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2478/amb-2023-0020>.
- Penchev D., D. Petkova, R. Zlatanova-Velikova, Public Opinion On Covid-19 Vaccines And Vaccination In Bulgaria, Sciences of Europe, No 109 (2023) ISSN 3162-2364, pp. 28-31.
- Baev M., D. Tsenov, G. Stoilchev, M. Petrov, Interpersonal Communication About Immunization, Handbook for Health Workers, Ed. Astra Forum Foundation, Sofia 2022, ISBN: 978-619-92312-2-7, p. 198